

Fast Fourier Transform Analysis of a Wind Farm having Doubly Fed Induction Generator initiated by wind turbine

¹Ishaan Mathur, ²Shravani Mathur, ³Dr. Shilpam Saxena, ⁴Dr. Pooja Singh, ⁵Ritika L Modi, ⁶Ritambhara Parashar

¹UG Scholar, ²Associate Professor, ³Professor, ⁴Professor, ⁵Assistant Professor, ⁶Assistant Professor
¹Department of Electronics & Communication,
¹UIT, RGPV, Bhopal, India

Abstract: Renewable energy is becoming an inseparable part of today's electricity generation as it is free of cost, no pollution creation and its abundant in nature. Using wind farms for distributed generation in remote areas are providing various advantages over the conventional ones. In this paper, we have used VI measurements at three levels B575V, B25KV, B120KV and a pi line of 30 Km 25KV feeder connected to a doubly fed Induction generator started wind turbine, which installs a rotor side converter, grid side converter and choke. WTDFIG finally supplies the real power to grid and receives reactive power from the grid at nominal cost. Simulation of the above is done in MATLAB and FFT analysis is also done to get the THD values for different voltage waveforms of the system.

IndexTerms - Affordable and clean energy, windfarm, DFIG driven wind turbine, Doubly fed Induction Generator Wind Turbine

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, we use wind farms to supply power to remote areas. Using the combination of six wind turbines, electricity can be generated at this power has to be stepped up with the transformer so to reduce the transmission losses as if voltage is high then current is low and hence lower Ohmic losses. Two converters are used to convert AC to DC and then this dc is smoothed down and again passed through an inverter to convert it to AC.

2. WIND FARM USING DFIG INITIATED WIND TURBINE

A nine mega-watt wind farm consisting of six 1.5 mega-watt wind turbines is attached to a 25 kilo-volt distribution system which gives power to a 120 kilo-volt power grid through a 30 kilo-meter, 25 kilo-volt feeder.

Wind turbines having Induction generator which is doubly fed (DFIG), wound rotor typed and an AC to DC to AC Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor typed Pulse width modulation converter. The stator winding is attached directly to the 60 Hz power grid and the rotor is given a varying frequency through the AC to DC to AC converter. The DFIG system confirms generation of maximum energy from the wind for lesser wind speeds by optimizing the turbine speed, and minimizing the mechanical stresses on the turbine during heavy winds.

In this paper, we have considered the constant wind speed of 15 meter per second. The control system utilises a controller of torque for maintaining the speed at 1.2 per unit. The generated reactive power of the wind turbine is regulated at zero mega volt ampere reactive. The sample time required to discretize the Simulink model ($T_s = 50$ micro seconds) is given in the Initialization tab of the Model Configuration Properties.

In "DFIG Wind Turbine" section, the data of the Induction generator must be given, then load the data to the (AC to DC to AC) converter and finally to turbine. The control systems and the drive train has been shown separately. In the Display section, check

the box "Display wind turbine power characteristics" to get the C_p curves of the turbine which are shown in diagram 7. The power of Turbine, the ratio of tip speed λ and the C_p values are given in diagram 8, as the function of speed of wind. At wind speed of 15 meter per second, the output power of turbine is one per unit of its rated power, the angle of pitch is 8.7 degrees and the speed of generator is 1.2 per unit. The power in wind can be calculated by the kinetic energy of the air mass flowing per unit time.

$$P_{air} = (\text{airmass per unit time})(\text{velocity})^2$$

$$= P_{air} = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3$$

3. CONVERTER ON GRID SIDE

To make DC link voltage constant, reference current i_{gd}^* is governed by proportional Integration controller.

$$i_{gd}^* = (K_{p1} + \frac{K_{i1}}{s})(V_{dc}^* - V_{dc})$$

$$V_d = (K_{p2} + \frac{K_{i2}}{s})(I_{gd}^* - I_{gd})$$

$$V_q = (K_{p2} + \frac{K_{i2}}{s})(I_{gq}^* - I_{gq})$$

The reactive power for DFIG shall be given by converter on grid side and reactive power from grid is set to zero.

Three phase programmable voltage source of 120KV, then three phase mutual inductance of 2500 MVA, $X_0/X_1=3$, Then three phase VI measurement B120, three phase transformer two winding star delta connected 120KV/25KV, 47MVA, Grounding transformer having a RLC branch with resistance 3.3Ω , again three phase VI measurement of 25KV B25 which is now connected to three phase Pi section line, again a delta star transformer and B575V is connected to DFIG Wind Turbine which is connected to Bus selector to select the output signals like DC Voltage, rotational speed, Real and reactive powers in per unit

DFIG driven by wind turbine is shown in fig2. Which consists of rotor side and grid side converter (RSC and GSC)

4. MATLAB SIMULATION

MATLAB model has been displayed which shows the detailed model. The detailed model consists of detailed blocks of power electronics Insulated gate bipolar transistor converters. Grid side converters and rotor side converters are shown connected by a capacitance. To get a viable accuracy with the 1620 hertz and 2700 hertz switching frequencies of both the converters used in this model, it should be discretized at a comparatively lesser time step (5 microseconds). This model is quite adapted for looking into the total harmonic distortion index and dynamic performance of control system over comparatively smaller periods of time (generally hundred milliseconds to approximately one second).

We would observe the steady-state operation of the Doubly fed Induction Generator and its dynamic performance due to a voltage drop because of a fault which occurred in remote area on the 120 kilo-volt system. In "120 kV" block of three phase programmable voltage source, we would see a voltage drop which is programmed at time $t=0.03$ second having value of six cycle 0.5 per unit.

Starting simulation, see the waveforms of voltage and current on the Scope. At this point of time, the "xInitial" variable which is having the starting variables is automatically programmed from the file given in the Model Configuration Properties therefore, the simulation is started in steady state condition.

At starting point, the Doubly fed Induction generator wind farm gives nine Megawatt. The corresponding speed of turbine is 1.2 per unit of synchronous speed of Generator. The Direct Current voltage is 1150 V and reactive power is regulated at zero mega volt ampere reactive. At time, $t=0.03$ second, the positive sequence voltage suddenly lowers down to 0.5 per unit, impacting an oscillation on the Direct current bus voltage and on the Doubly fed Induction generator's power output. At the time of the voltage drop, the control system regulates DC voltage and reactive power at their given points (1150 V, 0 MVAR). The system is recovered in four cycles.

Fig1. MATLAB/SIMULINK model of 9 mega-watt wind farm using DFIG initiated by wind turbine.

Fig2. Doubly fed Induction Generator fed Wind Turbine

Fig3. Wind Turbine

Fig4. MATLAB model of drive train

Fig5. Asynchronous machine per unit model

Electrical and mechanical model of Asynchronous Machine has been shown. Further the speed and electromechanical torque can be calculated from mechanical model.

5. RESULT

The waveforms of voltage and current can be observed on scope for B575V, B25KV. The output dc voltage, rotational speed, Real and reactive power components

Fig6. Waveforms of windfarms supplying grid

Fig7. Wind turbine characteristics where pitch angle increases by step of 2 degree

Fig8. Wind turbine characteristics when pitch angle is increased by step of 2 degree with wind speed of 1.2 per unit

Fig9. FFT Analysis of distributed generation by wind farms

6. CONCLUSION

This can be easily seen from the results that the total harmonic distortion for current and voltage waveforms can be calculated by clicking on powergui block and select FFT Analysis tool. By varying the various blocks values, one can achieve lower THD values also which is helpful in mitigating power quality issues of renewable sources generated and transmitted power to grid. At this instant, value of THD is 13.20.

7. APPENDIX

Every data is considered for one turbine	
Number of wind turbines	6
Generator data:	
Power	1.5e6W
Stator's resistance and reactance(p.u.)	[0.023 0.18]
Rotor's resistance and reactance(p.u.)	[0.016 0.16]
Magnetizing Inductance Lm	2.9
Inertia Constant	0.685
Friction factor	0.01
Pair of poles	3
Converter data	
Maximum current of grid converter (pu of generated nominal current)	0.8
coupling Inductor of grid [L, R] (p.u.)	[0.3 0.003]
DC Nominal bus voltage (V)	1150
DC bus capacitance	10000e-6
Line filter Capacitance (Q=50) (var)	120e3
Turbine data;	
Mechanical nominal output power (W)	1.5e6
speed of wind at nominal speed and at Cp maximum value	11m/s
Starting wind speed	11m/s
Drive train data:	

Inertia Constant of Wind turbine H(s)	4.32
Shaft spring constant referred to high speed shaft	1.11
mutual damping of Shaft	1.5
Turbine starting speed (p u of nominal speed)	1.2
Starting Torque Output	0.83
Controller data:	
Voltage regulator gains of DC bus [Kp, Ki]	[8 400]
Current regulator gains of Grid side converter	[0.83 5]
Speed regulator gains	[3 0.6]
Current regulator gains of Rotor side converter	[0.6 8]
Q and V regulator gains	[0.05 20]
Pitch controller gain	[150]
Compensation gains of Pitch	[3 30]
Frequency of grid side Pulse Width Modulation carrier wave	2700
Frequency of rotor side Pulse Width Modulation carrier wave	1620
Maximum pitch angle	27

8. REFERENCES

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